

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

DIRECTIONS FOR INCREASING THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF PRODUCTION IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN AGRICULTURE

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Abstract

In the modern world, it is impossible to imagine any field of activity, including agriculture, without the use of digital technologies. They have penetrated all areas of life and have become an important tool for increasing productivity, efficiency and sustainability. In the context of increasing world population, climate change and scarcity of natural resources, there is a need for more efficient use of existing resources. In this context, digital transformation is becoming a key factor that can ensure the sustainable development of agriculture. In this regard, the article examines the factors affecting the optimization of production processes, reduction of labor costs, increase of efficiency and improvement of product quality in the use of digital technologies in agriculture.

Keywords: agriculture, digital transformation, economic efficiency, etc.

Introduction

The use of digital technologies in agriculture is carried out through the integration of various systems that help optimize production processes, reduce labor costs, increase efficiency and improve product quality.

Technologies have a contradictory role, both in facilitating unprecedented population growth and in providing a potential solution to emerging problems. The main challenges, which are geographically and technologically interconnected, must be overcome through future-oriented agriculture and technological progress. (Terziev, 2025)

In this regard, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated October 11, 2021, titled "On certain measures to improve governance in the fields of digitalization, innovation, high technologies, and communications in the Republic of Azerbaijan," was also issued.(1)

The Internet of things is becoming an increasingly important tool for modern agriculture. IoT devices are used to collect data from fields and livestock complexes, monitor the condition of soil and plants, automate irrigation, fertilization, and other processes. They also help farmers optimize resource use and reduce risks (Torikov, 2022).

Artificial intelligence is used to predict weather conditions, crop yields, determine optimal times and methods for planting and harvesting, recognize plant and animal diseases, etc. (Borisov, 2020).

Big Data offers opportunities to improve production. It allows for the collection, storage and analysis of large amounts of information. This opens up new opportunities for process optimization, forecasting and

data-driven decision-making. For example, it allows farms to optimize fertilization processes and make decisions on the selection of optimal crop and soil cultivation methods. Data collected from drones, sensors and satellites allows monitoring plant health, identifying diseases, determining moisture and nutrient levels, which helps to respond to potential problems in a timely manner and optimize crop care.

Blockchain technology is used to ensure the transparency and security of information. This allows for the creation of reliable and auditable supply chains, as well as protection against fraud and other risks.

The essence and determinants of digital transformation

In economic literature, the essence of digital transformation is classified as follows:

1. Integration of technologies: The introduction of digital tools such as cloud technologies, artificial intelligence, big data, IoT (Internet of Things), automation, etc. into enterprise activities.

2. Customer orientation: Digital transformation promotes the creation of new digital platforms and services to improve user experience and customer satisfaction.

3. Efficiency and optimization: Digitalization of processes in order to increase labor productivity, reduce costs and accelerate decision-making.

4. Innovation and agility: Responding to new market demands and competition in a more agile and innovative way.

The following determinants can be identified in ensuring the transition to digital transformation in agriculture:

Table 1.

Key determinants of digital transformation

Determinants	Disclosure
Technological infrastructure	High-speed internet, servers, cloud services, IT systems, etc.
Human capital	IT-savvy workforce, digital skills and training programs
Leadership and management	Leaders open to digital change and strategic vision
Culture and openness to change	Rejection of traditional thinking and adaptation to innovations
Regulatory environment and policy	Legislation and government programs promoting digitalization
Financial resources	Financial opportunities for investment in technologies
Customer expectations	Increasing demand for modern, convenient and digital services
Competitive environment	Pressure from competitors using digital tools

Source: Compiled by the authors using the Bulletin "Digital Transformation in Azerbaijan – 2023".

The application of digital technologies in agriculture is already demonstrating its effectiveness in the context of sustainable development.

Digital transformation in agriculture can accelerate and improve various aspects—from collecting data from fields to helping the produce reach the market. It also helps farmers utilize geographic data to increase yield and automate manual tasks such as harvesting, sowing seeds, etc., using machinery. (Bhargav, 2025)

The ecological aspect of sustainable development is implemented through the use of precision farming technologies that optimize the use of water, fertilizer and energy, minimizing environmental damage. For example, with the help of sensors and data management systems, farmers can accurately determine where and when to apply fertilizers or water, reduce the total amount of resources used, prevent their unnecessary use and environmental pollution.

It is known that economic sustainability is achieved by increasing efficiency and reducing costs. Technologies such as autonomous tractors and drones can increase labor productivity, reduce fuel and maintenance costs. Big data analytics allow farmers to predict market trends and allocate resources in the most efficient way, increasing profitability and business sustainability.

Social sustainability is also improved through digital transformation. Access to digital markets and transparent supply chains helps small farmers improve their economic situation and sustainability. Distance learning technologies allow rural residents to expand access to knowledge and improve their skills.

The process of digital transformation of agriculture in Azerbaijan

The digital transformation of agriculture in Azerbaijan is a strategic process implemented through joint initiatives of the public and private sectors. This process involves the application of various digital technologies in the agricultural sector to increase productivity, efficiently use resources, and protect the environment.

The restoration and reconstruction works in the territories of Azerbaijan liberated from occupation are not limited to the rebuilding of physical infrastructure.

These areas are becoming exemplary sites for the implementation of "smart village" and "smart city" projects built on modern technologies.(2)

A number of digital transformation initiatives have been implemented in agriculture in Azerbaijan:¹

1. Electronic Agricultural Information System (EATIS)

The platform, launched in 2019, provides farmers with easy access to services such as subsidies, seeds, fertilizers and product sales. This system allows more than 470,000 farmers to register 719,000 hectares of land.

2. "Dost Agropark" - Smart Agriculture Project

This project, implemented by Turkish and Azerbaijani investors in the Zangilan and Gubadli regions, contributes to the development of livestock farming in addition to wheat, barley and corn production. The project revitalizes the agricultural and livestock sectors in the Karabakh and Zangezur regions.

3. "Agali" Smart Village Project

This project, implemented in the village of Agali in the Zangilan region, allows farmers to manage their irrigation and gas systems via a mobile application. The project covers not only agriculture, but also residential and infrastructure sectors.

4. Application of Blockchain Technology

A pilot project implemented by the Ministry of Agriculture of Azerbaijan provides seed producers with unique labels (with QR codes). This system allows them to track the quality and origin of seeds.

5. Smart Agriculture Cooperation with South Korea

The Ministry of Agriculture of Azerbaijan has signed a memorandum of cooperation with South Korea's KOTRA and other companies. This cooperation includes the application of "SmartFarm" technologies and the development of cloud systems.

6. "Precision Agriculture with Trichoderma" Technology

This technology, implemented with the equipment of the Austrian company APV, ensures the use of accurate amounts of fertilizers and plant growth regulators. This approach helps protect the environment and increase productivity.

Azerbaijan has identified digital transformation in agriculture as a priority area since 2020. In this regard, we can note that the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) has evaluated Azerbaijan's experience in the field of e-agriculture as the best practice.

As a result of implementing all this, it is possible to ensure food security, increase export potential, achieve equitable development across regions, and digitally restore rural jobs.

It should also be noted that the following data sources can be used for the economic assessment of the impact of digital transformation on economic efficiency in the agricultural sector:

- State Statistical Committee
- Agrarian Credit and Development Agency (AKIA)
- Ministry of Agriculture
- EKTIS (eagro.az)
- FAO and UNDP reports

Problems in implementing digital transformation

The digital transformation of agriculture opens up new opportunities to increase the efficiency and sustainability of the agricultural sector. However, it also creates a number of serious problems and challenges that require attention and solutions.

The first and most obvious obstacles to digital transformation are technical and technological issues. First, many technologies require significant investments in infrastructure and equipment, which may be inaccessible to many farmers, especially in developing countries. Second, most digital technologies require reliable and fast internet access, which can be a problem in rural areas. Third, the use of new technologies requires specific skills and knowledge that many farmers do not have.

There are also social and economic barriers to implementing digital transformation. On the one hand, many farmers may be resistant to change, fearing job losses or distrusting new technologies. On the other hand, digital transformation can widen the gap between large and small farmers, which can lead to increased economic inequality and social problems in rural communities. Finally, as we mentioned above, digital transformation raises questions about data security and privacy. The collection and processing of large amounts of data, including farmers' personal data and business details, can be subject to misuse and attack. This is especially true in cloud and IoT environments, where data is transmitted and stored outside the local network.

All these challenges and problems require attention and solutions from various participants in the process - from farmers to technology developers, government agencies and international organizations. Only by joint efforts can we overcome these barriers and fully realize the potential of digital transformation for agriculture.

Methodology for assessing the economic efficiency of digital transformation in agriculture.

Various indicators and formulas are used to calculate the economic efficiency of production in the context of digital transformation in agriculture. These for-

mulas measure economic efficiency by taking into account aspects such as resource optimization, productivity increase and cost reduction.

The main directions of economic assessment of the impact of digital transformation on economic efficiency in the agricultural sector can be shown as follows:

1. Productivity increase
2. Cost reduction
3. Labor productivity increase
4. Income growth and market access
5. Return on investment (ROI)

1. The basic formula of economic efficiency (Productivity / Efficiency ratio):

$$\text{Economic Efficiency} = \frac{\text{Cost of production}}{\text{Production costs}}$$

Here:

The cost of production is found by multiplying the market price of the product by the output of the product (for example, output (tons) × price).

2. Calculation of productivity (Yield):

$$\text{Productivity} = \frac{\text{Final product volume}}{\text{Used area hectares}}$$

Increased productivity through digital technologies directly increases economic efficiency.

3. Revenue Increase Report:

To calculate the change in revenue after implementing digital transformation:

$$\Delta R = R_{\text{after}} - R_{\text{before}}$$

or in percentage:

$$\% \Delta R = \frac{R_{\text{after}} - R_{\text{before}}}{R_{\text{before}}} \times 100\%$$

3. Cost Reduction Percentage:

$$\% \Delta C = \frac{C_{\text{before}} - C_{\text{after}}}{C_{\text{before}}} \times 100\%$$

5. Indicator of economic efficiency of production (Return on Investment, ROI):

$$\text{ROI} = \frac{\text{Investment income} - \text{Investment cost}}{\text{Investment cost}} \times 100\%$$

Here:

Investment return — the additional income generated as a result of the funds spent on digital transformation.

Investment cost — the total cost spent on the implementation of digital technologies.

6. Calculating resource efficiency:

Digital technologies increase water efficiency by optimizing irrigation management. For example, the change in costs and productivity as a result of reducing water use for irrigation is calculated as follows:

$$\text{Water efficiency} = \frac{\text{Product volume}}{\text{Amount of water used (m}^3\text{)}}$$

In order to assess the economic efficiency of agricultural production in the context of digital transformation, these formulas measure costs, revenues, productivity and investment efficiency. Also, big data and real-time monitoring systems are applied for data analysis.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Thus, the digital transformation of agriculture opens up new opportunities for sustainable development, balancing economic efficiency, social justice and environmental sustainability. The evolution of digital technologies such as the Internet of Things, artificial

intelligence, big data and blockchain is leading to significant changes in agricultural practices, facilitating the tracking and management of resources, improving product quality and increasing incomes.

However, the analysis shows that the transformation also brings to the fore a number of problems and challenges. Technical and technological barriers, social and economic problems, as well as data security issues require careful and thoughtful approaches. Solving these problems requires the cooperation of various actors, from farmers and technology developers to government agencies and international organizations.

It is important for Azerbaijan to maintain its competitiveness in the international arena and to adapt its policy for innovative development to the requirements of digital transformation. For this, security in cyberspace must be ensured, primarily. That is, since the digitalization process is taking place rapidly, the cybersecurity of digital systems and networks must be ensured accordingly.

Also, the training of educated, skilled personnel in the field of cybersecurity should be kept in the spotlight. The above-mentioned will increase the confidence of the population both within the country and at the international level in the policy of our state in the field of digital transformation of the economy.

Based on the studies conducted, the following recommendations can be made:

1. Continuity of investment in research and development in the field of digital technologies for agriculture.
2. Promoting training and skills development for farmers and other agricultural entities in the field of digital technologies.
3. Development and implementation of standards and regulations for data protection and privacy in the context of digital agriculture.
4. Support the development of the infrastructure necessary for the application and use of digital technologies in rural areas.
5. Continue research in the field of digital transformation of agriculture, especially from a sustainable development perspective.

References

1. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated October 11, 2021, "On certain measures to improve governance in the fields of digitalization, innovation, high technologies, and communications in the Republic of Azerbaijan."
2. The Digitalization Era in Azerbaijan: From "Industry 4.0" to "Smart Village." 2025

3. Fətullayeva, A.G. (2024). *Digital Transformation in Azerbaijan – 2023* Bulletin. Baku: "Elm və Bilik" Publishing House, 64 pp. ISBN: 978-9952-549-19-5.

4. Mikayılova, N. (July 2025). "Trends in the Digitalization of the Agricultural Sector." *Agricultural Economics*, No. 1 (47), p. 46.

5. Popov, E.V. (2021). Levels of digital maturity of industrial enterprise / E.V. Popov, V.L. Simonova, V.V. Cherepanov // *Journal of New Economy*. — 2021. — T. 22, No. 2. — С. 88–109. EDN GUAORR.

6. Kuzmich, N.P. (2023). Change of labor conditions in the agrarian sphere as a result of digital transformation of rural economy // *Economy, work, management in rural economy*. 2023. No. 3(97). С. 201–207. EDN LDOZCK.

7. Mineeva, L.N. (2023). Transformation of agriculture: problems and digital opportunities of rural territories // *Modern Economy Success*. 2023. No. 2. С. 36–41. EDN DNRJDK.

8. Borisov, E.A. (2020). Digital land management as a fundamental condition of digital transformation of rural economy. // *Евразийское Научное объединение*. 2020. No. 5-7(63). С. 561–563. EDN GZRAZV.

9. Dambaeva, I.Zh. (2023). Problems and conditions of phase barrier transition in digital transformation of rural economy // *Science and business: ways of development*. 2023. No. 2(140). С. 26–28. EDN PWUDSE.

10. Torikov, V.E. (2022). Состояние и перспективы двигательной трансформации сельского // *Vestnik of the Ryazan state agrotechnological university named after P.A. Kostycheva*. 2022. T. 14, No. С. 109–116. DOI 10.36508/RSATU.2022.54.2.013. EDN QGHKFC.

11. Terziev V.K. Digital Agriculture. Bytes against Hunger Translating local and personal approaches of digital agriculture – Access mode: <https://www.capgemini.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/>. *International Journal of Agricultural Science* <http://iaras.org/iaras/journals/ijas>. (Retrieved February 16, 2025)

12. Bhargav J. Digital Transformation in Agriculture: Best Practices and Examples. May, 2025 <https://linkedin.com/shareArticle?mini=true&title=Digital%20Transformation%20in%20Agriculture:%20Best%20Practices%20and%20Examples%20&url=https://www.leadsquared.com/industries/agriculture/digital-transformation-in-agriculture/>